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How Courts are Leading Change for Mining Law in BC with International Standards

Bell, Peter

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Abstract

Mining is a global industry where jurisdictions are endowed with different amounts of natural resources and then create institutional frameworks to regulate the extraction of their endowment by local or global entities. As metal prices reach all-time highs, there is more competition than ever among different jurisdictions to attract global investment and encourage local business development based on all aspects of mining. However, there is also an increase in the prevalence of international legal frameworks to create minimum standards for mining. For example, the province of British Columbia in Canada created a new law in 2019 that was used by the courts in 2023 to force the executive branch to make changes that the legislative branch was already working on to roll out in 2027. This article details the ongoing story of BC, where different branches of government interact with each other in new ways based on provincial laws that implement an international framework.

Keywords: Mining, BC, Canada, First Nations, Indigenous Peoples, United Nations, Taxes, Law

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How Courts are Leading Change for Mining Law in BC with International Standards

Mining is a global industry where jurisdictions are endowed with different amounts of natural resources and then create institutional frameworks to regulate the extraction of their endowment by local or global entities. As metal prices reach all-time highs, there is more competition than ever among different jurisdictions to attract global investment and encourage local business development based on all aspects of mining. However, there is also an increase in the prevalence of international legal frameworks to create minimum standards for mining. For example, the province of British Columbia in Canada created a new law in 2019 that was used by the courts in 2023 to force the executive branch to make changes that the legislative branch was already working on to roll out in 2027. This article details the ongoing story of BC, where different branches of government interact with each other in new ways based on provincial laws that implement an international framework.

The article by Acemoglu et al. (2020) highlights an idea from institutional economics called institutional persistence, where an institution can change over time, yet largely stay the same. This applies to mining law in BC, as it has some important common features since the 1800s Gold Rush Era regarding how mining claims are created. There are major changes to the letter of the law since the 1850s, but much of the spirit of the law is similar, and this creates problems for Canada's goals for reconciliation between Indigenous and non-Indigenous people. For example, the University of Victoria Environmental Law Centre (2021) describes eight recent cases where BC fails to secure First Nations for mining projects. We may be in a time of major changes based on new laws enacted in BC, court decisions based on these new laws, and changes by the executive branch of government in response to the courts. The current changes described in this article may seem small, but Acemoglu et al. (2020) find that the concept of path dependence applies to institutional economics; what seems like small changes now could have very large impacts in the future.

The book by Acemoglu & Robinson (2012) provides a further theoretical perspective that is useful for this article. They distinguish between two types of institutions: political ones that distribute and regulate power, and economic institutions that regulate property rights. In their theory, a fundamental driving force for economic development is the ability for businesses to protect gains from investment, versus the risk of expropriation or loss. This is a big issue in mining because you cannot move an orebody: if the government decide to increase taxes after the mine is built, then you cannot move the mine to another jurisdiction. An extreme historical example occurred when Chile nationalized copper mines owned by foreign companies in the 1970s. González et al. (2024) show this had a small net benefit to Chile over the next 50 years, but Edwards (2025) discusses how problematic this government action was in terms of opaque valuation metrics that led to foreign companies getting paid nothing for the mines. Nonetheless, the copper endowment in Chile is so important on a global basis that foreign companies continue to invest there today. Why does Teck Resources, the famous Canadian mining company, focus its current investment more on projects in Chile than in Canada?

What kind of mining do we want in BC? It is possible to describe the types of mines and mineral deposits we have in BC, then create models of how big the economic pie is for each project and how we can split the pies between various stakeholders to understand where policy encourages or discourages development. The government of BC needs to understand how the economic conditions for local mines compare to similar types of mines around the world to prepare for the competition among governments for policy design. Although the oil industry is different from mining, Norway provides important examples of Intergenerational Equity and the Public Trust Doctrine as described in (Basu, 2020). Why is the experience of Alberta so much different than Norway? Does the complicated patchwork of provincial vs federal jurisdiction in Canada create confusion that holds us back? To what degree should governments pursue incremental changes to patch over problems, versus attempting to redesign the Canadian institutional framework from first principles? Can we even agree on the first principles for mining in Canada today?

The Courts, The Legislative, and UNDRIP in BC

The Court of Appeal for British Columbia (2025) ruling provides essential information regarding the timeline of the ongoing story that is the focus of this article. The new legislation enacted in 2019, called the Declaration Act (Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples Act), was the “*first Canadian jurisdiction to enact a statute incorporating the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples into domestic law.*” (Court of Appeal for British Columbia, [4], 2025). This was a bold move that caused some debate at the time about whether the new law would allow the provincial courts to take on a quasi-legislative function by making rulings on other laws: apparently, the political leadership believed the courts would give the legislature enough time to make changes (Shaw, 2025). That assumption seems to have broken down the first time it was tested with this court case.

In the 2025 ruling by the Court of Appeal for British Columbia, one judge maintained this idea that the Declaration Act is not meant to allow courts to rule on the consistency of existing laws with the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, but the two other judges decided that the courts must make such a ruling. As described below, their decision was not about the mining law itself but about how the executive branch of government implements the law, which led to a quick fix but may have opened the door for more surprises.

In 2021, the BC legislature released the first draft action plan for how to implement the Declaration Act (Government of British Columbia, 2021), and it did not mention mining. In 2022, two separate lawsuits were filed by First Nations who argue the government violates the Declaration Act when creating mining claims without consulting them. Previously, the government required consultation when converting from a mining claim into a mining lease, but not when issuing a basic claim. The two First Nations had problems with companies staking claims in their territories, but had no legal way to stop them at the time; they argued in court that the Declaration Act provided them a way to do so. The final version of the action plan for how to implement the Declaration Act, published later in 2022 (Government of British Columbia, 2022), did include mining. In particular, it mentioned the need to reform the Mining Tenure Act.

In 2023, the first court decision was that the government must consult First Nations before creating mining claims in their territory and give the executive branch 18 months to change how claims are created (Court of Appeal for British Columbia, 2025). The judge determined that the law called the Mining Tenure Act was constitutionally valid, but the implementation by the Chief Gold Commissioner (CGC) was problematic (Court of Appeal for British Columbia, [29], 2025). It was possible to fix it without completely remaking the law, just by changing the policy of the executive branch. This fixed the initial problem driving the first court case, but the first court ruling did not address the broader question of whether the mining regime in BC was consistent with the Declaration Act.

By winning the first case, these two First Nations won the right for all First Nations in BC to have consultation before mining claims are issued in their (claimed) territory. However, the judge in the first court case did not decide whether the mining regime in BC was consistent with the Declaration Act or not and the cases were escalated to the Supreme Court for appeal. The decision of the Supreme Court was issued in early December 2025 and provided the landmark decision that the minerals regime in BC was inconsistent with the BC law called the Declaration Act. This conclusion (“*UNDRIP and the mineral claims regime are inconsistent,*” Court of Appeal for British Columbia, 2025) sounds like a shocking challenge to the fundamental legal basis of mining in BC, but what does it mean?

A key section of the Supreme Court judgement is provided below:

“It is the existence of inconsistency between a British Columbia law and one or more provisions of UNDRIP that triggers the Crown’s obligation to take action... Some such measures may require legislative action... In other cases, executive or administrative action may be sufficient. For example, in the circumstances in question in this case, the Crown could decide to reform the Mineral Tenure Act, which would mean placing proposed amendments before the Legislature, or the CGC could take action at the policy level.” (Court of Appeal for British Columbia, [149], 2025)

The first court decision determined that the Chief Gold Commissioner must require consultation before claims are created, but did not declare whether the mineral claims regime

was consistent with the Declaration Act. The Supreme Court ruled that the mineral claims regime is inconsistent and that something must be done, but it did not specify what exactly. The Supreme Court offers a few possible actions, such as requiring the Chief Gold Commissioner to change their policy to require consultation before issuing claims, as had already been done before the Supreme Court ruling. The language in this section of the Supreme Court ruling is designed to give the government as many ways as possible to deal with these kinds of legacy issues that are identified by the Declaration Act as quickly as possible.

Back in 2022, when the government published their final version of the action plan to implement the Declaration Act, the plan had a five-year timeline with a target date of 2027. For the Mining Tenure Act Reform, the government engaged the public in 2024 and 2025 to gather information on how to update the Mining Tenure Act. This public engagement happened before the public knew the outcome of the Supreme Court ruling published in December 2025, but after the public knew that the lower court determined the Chief Gold Commissioner was wrong to issue claims before consulting First Nations and requiring the Chief Gold Commissioner to change how claims were issued.

These court decisions have sparked a legal debate about the role of courts versus the legislative branch of government. In 2022, the legislative branch said they were working on this issue of consultation when they included Mineral Tenure Act Reform in their action plan. However, the original draft of the action plan in 2021 missed this issue completely. If the first court case had not happened in 2022, then this topic may never have appeared in the government's action plan at all. Also, note that the legislative branch required 5 years to review this issue among all others, whereas the court cases forced immediate action within 18 months of the first judgment. Clearly, the courts play an essential role in the ongoing changes to the nature of government in BC today.

One perspective on the Supreme Court was that the issue is moot because the Chief Gold Commissioner already made the changes at the heart of the original lawsuit. However, the First Nations pushed for an appeal because they wanted the court to clearly say “yes or no” whether

the existing laws in the Mineral Tenure Act are consistent with the Declaration Act or not. In the 2025 ruling, the Supreme Court determined that the mineral claims regime in BC is not consistent with the Declaration Act. Specifically, this meant that the way the executive branch implemented the policy through the Chief Gold Commissioner was problematic. However, the Mineral Tenure Act law itself was consistent with the Declaration Act and the Constitution (Court of Appeal for British Columbia, [29], 2025). As such, the Supreme Court ruling appears to have big implications for legal theory but no further immediate impact on BC mining because the original pain point was already resolved.

There may be a bigger issue hiding in the shadows behind this Supreme Court ruling based on the fact that the Declaration Act talks about ownership of minerals in Article 26, section 2 as follows: *“Indigenous peoples have the right to own, use, develop and control the lands, territories and resources that they possess by reason of traditional ownership or other traditional occupation or use, as well as those which they have otherwise acquired.”* I wonder if this section may have significant implications in future court cases or legislative changes. As detailed in the Court of Appeal for British Columbia (2025), the Crown owns the minerals now. However, what happens when there is no treaty with a particular First Nation? This time, the courts made the government consult before creating claims; next time, could the courts change the fundamental assumptions of who owns the minerals? Or who sets and collects taxes?

The summary of historical mineral tax revenue for the Government of British Columbia (2025) shows significant growth over time. Back in 2001, the total mineral tax was \$45 million, with the majority, \$27 million, from metals and the remainder, \$18 million, from coal. These amounts have been highly variable in recent years, reaching an all-time high in 2023 with a total mineral tax of \$817 million, where the majority was from coal, \$737 million, and the remainder from metals, \$79 million. This total was around 1% of total government revenue, which was \$84 billion in 2025. In contrast, total GDP for BC was around \$429 billion, with approximately \$11 billion from mining. Coal activity has declined in recent years, and coal taxes declined approximately 75% to \$182 million in 2025. The size of the pie is changing drastically for mining taxes in BC. Will we see the big changes to how the pie is cut up in the years ahead?

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